

Impact of Service Marketing Mix Elements on Tourists' Satisfaction During Covid-19: An Empirical Study in the Eastern Part of Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Covid-19 has created humungous negative effects on the well-being of people, society, the world economy, and this study's point of interest-tourism sector around the world. Very little research in the context of Bangladesh has explored the impact of this pandemic has on tourists. As a result, the purpose of this study is to explain the function that the service marketing mix elements (7Ps) play toward the degree of satisfaction of the tourists from the perspective of the eastern region of Bangladesh. In doing so, the determinants of 7Ps towards tourists' satisfaction were also discovered, and their indirect consequences on the tourist sector were explored. A questionnaire for a survey was given to 250 people who had visited the eastern area of Bangladesh. A seven-factor model was suggested, and multivariate regression analysis was used to find several independent variables that could be used to predict or explain the dependent variable. For the first time in the eastern region of Bangladesh, a study has examined the impact of service marketing mix aspects on tourists' satisfaction, offering empirical proof at a time of crisis. The findings of the study reveal that tourists' satisfaction is favorably correlated with service marketing mix factors. This research gives practical advice for tourist marketers to design the 7Ps and to develop and maintain sustainable and profitable tourist relationships.

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Introduction

COVID-19 outbreak in 2019 was a turning moment for the tourism industry all over the world. Due to this pandemic situation transports were banned, country borders were closed, people were strictly asked to be in their home, all sorts of events were also put on halt (Scott and Hall, 2020). These restrictions pushed the economic growth downwards, and the sales were also gradually going very low. Although the impact of this pandemic in the tourism sector might be seen as insignificant compared to the deteriorating condition of public health, and global recession, many countries depend on their tourism industry for development and even for financial growth. Obviously, the tourism industry is keen to get back to their normal activities as soon as possible. This industry is tied up with service, service has direct relationship with the economic stability of this sector (Hidayat, 2010). Several industries that require service such as- banking, insurance, telecommunication provides the dynamics of the service sector and tourism has to be related for the development. The purpose of marketing service is to create consumer expectation (Daryanto, 2013). The company then thrives to meet the expectation they has set, as the consumers' satisfaction is the result of the comparison between their perception of the service and the expectations (Daryanto, 2013). A lot of factors can influence the degree of tourist satisfaction, that includes service marketing mix elements (product, price, place, promotion, people, process, physical evidence) and quality of service, some of those studies are-(Azhar and Jufrizen, 2017), (Setiawan and Suyuti, 2017), (Tefera and Govender, 2015); (Nurcahyo et al., 2017); (Kwok et al., 2016); (Rahayu, 2015); (Sukmadi et al., 2014); (Liu and Yen, 2010); (Permatasari et al., 2017). Bangladesh is a densely populated country located in south-central Asia. Bangladesh is bordered by some of the states of India, Myanmar and its southern part opens into the Bay of Bengal. The southern region of Bangladesh is infringed by the Sundarbans. The eastern region can be divided into two parts- northeast and southeast which are Sylhet and Chittagong, Cumilla respectively. Chittagong offers both hills and oceans. The hill areas have lofty mountains, tallest peak, dense forest, indigenous lifestyle of tribal people, their culture and colorful festivals, visitors feel they are in the kingdom of clouds. Cox's Bazar is the largest unbroken sea beach in the world, also in Chittagong. It can be referred to as the tourist capital of Bangladesh. Everyday a heft number of people visit its beaches to soak in the beauty of sunrise and golden sunset from around the world. Another serene attraction, also known as the pearl of the sea-Saint Martin -the only coral island of Bangladesh. Only 8 km of landmass amazes with its crystal clear blue water. Then there is Boga Lake which is believed to be made of rainwater, Rangamati, Kaptai Lake and Patenga. Cumilla is a city of Chittagong division, supremely known and visited for its archaeological beauty. Various archaeological relics from the 7th -8 th century were found here and now are preserved in the Maynamati Museum. There is a cemetery from World War II, which is maintained by the Commonwealth War Grave Commission. In the northeast we have Sylhet division. An array of exotic places to visit ranging from tea-estates to waterfalls, fountains, lakes, water reservoirs, swamp forest can be found in Sylhet. Ratargul swamp forest-one of the best freshwater swamp forests in the world proves that silence can be enjoyable, Lalakhal, Baikka beel, Madhobpur lake are some serene and tranquil places to visit in Sylhet. A major nature reserve, Lawachara National Park is also located here. As the tourism industry is growing, to attract more domestic and international tourists to visit these places, many facilities and infrastructures are being built. The emergence of this industry is playing a pivotal role in the economic development of the country, decreasing the unemployment rate, eradicating poverty. During COVID outbreak the tourism sector of Bangladesh was also shattered. However in Bangladesh, very few studies are done on this issue of marketing mix elements and tourist satisfaction in the time of COVID-19. Hence, this study is pivotal as it will help the tourism marketers and government to combat this situation and figure out ways to redefine the 7P so that they can ensure enhanced tourists' satisfaction by giving good quality

service and offering. An in-depth study is required to know and manage the tourism sector fittingly and proficiently so that the tourists of eastern part of Bangladesh can be kept happy and content. The aim of the study is to find out the connection between service marketing mix and its effect on the satisfaction level of tourists visiting tourist spots of Eastern Bangladesh during the Covid-19 pandemic situation.

Literature Review

The COVID-19 crisis is affecting market cash flows, supply chains, and action plans all over the world (Abideen et al., 2020; Azlan et al., 2020; Bakar and Ramli, 2020). In particular, the tourism and hospitality industries are sensitive to these kinds of global challenges and should come up with good ways to deal with them (Ritchie and Jiang, 2019). Gursoy and Chi (2020); Rivera (2020) The tourism and hospitality industries suffer from a worldwide crash in revenues, demands, and occupancy rates. Due to the fact that the crisis is still going on, it is hard to say how things will change. So, people in charge of making decisions in the tourism and hospitality industries need to make sure they are following the WHO's recommendations and both local and international rules. It is expected that how satisfied tourists are with the services offered will depend on how their expectations change. A number of factors were identified in pre-covid time which were responsible for tourist's satisfaction like tourists' perceptions (Sianipar et al., 2021); safety and security (Hossain and Nesa, 2022); natural scenery (Cheng et al. 2022); Service Quality (Hong et al. 2020) and so on. Though the service marketing factors were used to measure the satisfaction level of tourists but in this crisis moment the number is few considering the eastern part of Bangladesh. Elements of the service marketing mix show that tourists' satisfaction with the services they're given changes as their expectations change (Oliver, 1980). So, depending on the service marketing mix model, we think that in the existing crisis, tourists' satisfaction will vary depending on how the tourism marketer changes the 7Ps. Researchers identified that the COVID-19 situation created a major impact on the global tourism industry (Deb et al., 2020). Both inbound and outbound tourism suffered from loss in Bangladesh. All flights were canceled by airlines, and hotels were nearly vacant, which resulted in huge financial loss and unemployment in the tourism sector of Bangladesh. The economy of Bangladesh to some extent relies on tourism. In the year 2019, 2.7% of Bangladesh's GDP was a contribution of the tourism and travel industry and it added 2.9% to the total employment of the country (WTTC, 2021). In addition to that, the tourism marketers and policymakers of Bangladesh should concentrate on increasing the degree of tourist satisfaction to assure recovery and feasibility of this sector.

Tourists' Satisfaction

Tourist satisfaction is a measurement that reflects how pleased consumers are with the offerings of a business and its capabilities. It is described as a measurement that determines how happy tourists are with a company. When consumers are satisfied with the product or service they receive, they are more likely to return for more and create a long-term relationship with a company (Chadee, 1996). People learn about the quality of the companies offering from the feedback of satisfied clients. On the other side, tourists who are dissatisfied serve as a constant reminder to firms that they have poor performance. A higher level of tourist satisfaction has been shown to boost brand loyalty (Shanka, 2012).

Service Marketing Mix

Marketing is a concentrated collection of actions and processes that clients recognize, which aids in the development of connections with them and which assists the firm as a whole (Al-Debi and Ashraf, 2014). Marketing aims to keep current clients and attract new purchases by satisfying them. With the use of marketing mix strategies, firms are able to accomplish their

goals by increasing their revenue and profits (Othman et al. 2018). The term "marketing mix" represents a set of different marketing instruments that may be controlled and that are utilized by marketers to accomplish their business goals (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010). The traditional 4ps was developed for manufacturing industries but the inadequacy of this in the service sector led to the expansion of additional 3ps named people, process and physical evidence (Booms and Bitner, 1964). Businesses that grasp the marketing mix factors may influence their current clients to continue their relationship and thus become long-term consumers. Bringing the 7Ps concept into practice involves making a concerted effort to strengthen the function that marketing plays in generating maximum profitability (Sadq, 2019).

Product and Tourists' Satisfaction

Armstrong and Kotler (2006) defined product as, "Anything that can be offered to a market for attention, acquisition, use, or consumption that might satisfy a want or need." The product constitutes locations and their natural landscape, as well as their facilities and infrastructure, mobility, and the impression of their attractiveness (Fyall and Garrod, 2005). Product includes hotel decor, room amenities, food & drink, employee service, and atmosphere (Vassiliadis, 2008; Meltem et al., 2010). In tourism, tourists buy a bundle of offerings rather than a single offering (Lewis and Chambers, 1984). The tourist product is made up of both physical and intangible qualities, each of which comes with its own set of advantages and characteristics (Rodriguez, 2014; Markgraf, 2015). Companies can differentiate their offerings and gain a competitive advantage by ensuring unique features of their product and services.

H₁: Product and tourists' satisfaction are positively related to each other.

Price and Tourists' Satisfaction

Price is considered a different marketing mix element compared to the others because only price denotes a revenue-generating factor whereas others generate cost for the business. "Price is the amount of money charged for a product or service, or the total values that consumers exchange for the benefits of having or using the product or service (Kotler et. Al, 2008). According to Peter and Donnelly (2007), When considering several aspects of a product or service, consumers place the most emphasis on price relative to other considerations. Because of the intangibility nature of a service, it is difficult to set the price of service than goods. According to Markgraf (2015) it's a good idea to fit the price of a product with the qualities it offers. The price mix of tourist products was the subject of some research (Reid and Bojanic, 2010; Devashish, 2011).

H₂: Price is positively associated with tourists' satisfaction.

Place and Tourists' Satisfaction

"Place" refers to the trade channels that allow tourists to get a tourism product and make a purchase order for it, confirm their reservation, and make payment for it (Middleton, 2001; Rodriguez, 2013). It may also be regarded in related to the physical geography or of the availability and accessibility of the information. Distribution of tourism goods and services entails travel by tourists to reach the offering because of the nature of tourism services, such as trade exhibitions, websites, resellers, direct mail, tourist destinations, etc. (Rodriguez, 2013). Musa and Adamu (2011) found that the expansion of tourism is significantly influenced by the availability of various modes of transportation.

H₃: Place significantly influence the tourists' satisfaction level.

Promotion and Tourists' Satisfaction

According to Lovelock and Wright (2002) promotion mix includes advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, PR, and direct marketing. A communication program informs, persuades, and

motivates target clients. The promotional activities have the potential to affect not only the tourists' perceptions, but also their feelings, their experiences, and their purchase patterns. Lovelock and Gummesson (2004) found that communication tools are extremely significant in the marketing of services because they contribute to the creation of compelling images as well as a feeling of trustworthiness, confidence, and comfort. Godfrey and Clarke (2000) note the importance of tour operators and travel agencies as middlemen in the tourism business. Without good communication, prospects may never learn about a service organization, what it offers, or how to utilize its products. Abd El Jalil (2010) found that brochures with physical attractions attract foreign travelers.

H4: Promotion and tourists' satisfaction are associated with each other.

People and Tourists' Satisfaction

In the hotel industry, people's actions, quality control, and personal selling are at the center of all that happens. In most cases, individuals are unable to separate from the whole service (Kotler, 2007). Zeithaml et al. (2006) found that people are the most important stakeholders, including the client, another tourist, and the employees of the tourist company. As a result, Reid and Bojanic (2010) claimed that people raise the level of tangibility achieved by the combination of the product and the service and Amin and Islam (2017) added that even in niche sectors, consumer satisfaction is influenced by a company's attitude, ability, and look with the labor-intensive nature of tourism, a tourist's connection with local communities and well-trained employees working in those places is critical to their overall experience (UNWTO, 2007). According to Armando (2005), effective service providers may meet customers' banking needs via 'face-to-face' engagement.

H5: Tourists' satisfaction is influenced by the people.

Process and Tourists' Satisfaction

The implementation of processes makes life simpler for tourist firms and enables tourist to obtain services in the most expedient and uncomplicated manner possible (Rodriguez, 2013). Process relates to service delivery methods, flow of activities, and processes (Zeithaml et al., 2006). Process describes how something is done. Hirankitti et al. (2009) said the client can tell the speed and expertise of service providers. It determines buyer satisfaction along with consistent service quality.

H6: Process is positively associated with Tourists' Satisfaction.

Physical Evidence and Tourists' Satisfaction

It is not possible to present services like commodities. tourist frequently rely on tangible cues or physical evidence to evaluate a service before making a purchase of it and to gauge their level of satisfaction with the service both during and after it has been consumed. This is because the intangible qualities of the service make such evaluations difficult. Evidence that can be readily connected with the product is considered to be physical evidence. Physical environment is where tourists and companies interact to provide service (Zeithaml et al., 2006). The existence of physical evidence is dependent on the traveller's experience, the accommodation, and the level of comfort in Tourism Kannan and Srinivasan (2009). In order for a product or service to be consumed and sold, it must be seen in its environment (Bachelor of Management Studies Team, 2014).

H7: Physical evidence is positively associated with Tourists' Satisfaction.

Research Questions

The authors of this study posed a number of research questions, each of which was guided by the particular aims of the problem, the theoretical framework, and the analytical model that was used in this investigation. These are-

- What aspects of the eastern portion of Bangladesh contribute to the overall positive experience that visitors have there?
- How much do factors such as product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence influence the level of satisfaction experienced by tourists?
- How can a marketer for tourism work on improving the listed factors to increase the degree of satisfaction felt by tourists?

Research Gap

There were a significant number of researches done on visitors' satisfaction during the COVID-19. But this study mainly focuses on the service marketing mix, where the process and promotion and service satisfaction components were shown from a new angle to identify the tourist satisfaction level. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the study on tourist satisfaction based on the eastern part of Bangladesh did not find any evidence of it. This is because domestic and foreign tourists are drawn to the beaches, animals, culture, and nature of the region. The results of the investigation will help to close this contextual gap.

Conceptual Framework

This study examined at tourist satisfaction as the dependent variable and tested a model of tourist satisfaction with seven independent variables of the service marketing mix.

Figure 1: Service Marketing Mix Elements and Tourists' Satisfaction

Methodology of the Study

The location of the study was in the eastern region of Bangladesh in several districts namely Cox's Bazar, Rangamati, Bandarban, Khagrachori, and Cumilla. All of the people that participated in this study were visitors who were travelling to these different tourist destinations. This study makes use of both primary and secondary sources of information. The primary data have been gathered through interviews with members of the relevant authorities,

tourists, tour operators, industry experts, and local residents. The secondary data have been gathered from a variety of sources, including published theses, books, journals, daily newspapers, and websites, as well as the publications of Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (BPC), Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, Bangladesh Bank, and the respective ministry. As the population is not known total of 250 respondents (N=250) were chosen using the convenience sampling method in order to meet the objectives of this study. According to Hoe (2008), a multivariate study should examine a sample size of greater than 200 to analyze data. A sample size between 30 and 500 is appropriate, and the minimum number of samples for multivariate analysis and multiple regressions should be ten times or more the number of variables utilized in the study (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010; Sekaran, 2003). According to this rule of thumb, the study's sample size should be at least 80 (8 x 10). The rule of thumb is finally implemented, but the number is three times greater. Based on prior literature, a structured questionnaire was designed. Two components comprised the questionnaire. First component includes respondents' age, gender, occupation, education level, marital status and income level. Second half of the questionnaire comprised 34 questions about marketing mix factors (product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical proof) and 4 questions about tourists's satisfaction. Respondents checked 38 statements. All factors were assessed using SPSS 22 on a 5-point likert scale (1= strongly agree to 5= strongly disagree) to gauge people's opinions and satisfaction (Fisher, 2010). The survey's answer scale spans from A preliminary survey with thirty (30) participants was carried out with the purpose of evaluating the reliability of the questionnaire and removing any room for ambiguity.

Table1: Relationship Between Service Marketing mix and Tourist Satisfaction

Service Marketing Mix elements with Tourist Satisfaction	Relationship Status	Findings	Field	Source	Year
Product, Price, Place, Promotion	Positive Relation	Simplify Marketing Activities, meet customer Requirements	General	Chai Lee Goi	2009
Product, promotion, place, price	Positive Relation	positive effects on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction	Food and beverage products of SME	Sudari et. al	2019
All the elements	Significant positive impact	a reliable and accurate measuring device and a good fit	Banking Sector	Khatab et. al	2019
quality of service, service orientation, and strategy marketing mix	mediation effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty	companies must first need to understand what the customer needs through variable service quality, service orientation, and marketing mix strategy	Telecommunication Industry	Solimun et. al	2018
product, process and physical evidence	significantly related to customer satisfaction	process is the most influential driver while price is the least influential	Retail Bank	Mohammad	2015

Data Analysis

Table 2: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	185	74.0
	Female	65	26.0
Age	Less than 30	164	65.6
	30-40	52	20.8
	40-50	22	8.8
	50-60	6	2.4
	Above 60	6	2.4

Occupation	Student	131	52.4
	Business	13	5.2
	Service holder	89	35.6
	Other	17	6.8
Educational Level	HSC	14	5.6
	Graduate	39	15.6
	Post-graduate	78	31.2
	Others	119	47.6
Marital Status	Married	83	33.2
	Single	159	63.6
	Widowed	3	1.2
	Divorced	5	2.0
Income level	Ten thousand Plus	70	28.0
	Twenty thousand Plus	75	30.0
	Thirty thousand Plus	46	18.4
	Forty thousand Plus	22	8.8
	Fifty thousand Plus	37	14.8
Number of Visit	Less than Three	61	24.4
	Three to five	83	33.2
	More than Five	106	42.4
Duration of Stay	Less than three	121	48.4
	Three to six	97	38.8
	Seven and above	32	12.8
Reason for Visiting	Business	19	7.6
	Tourism	223	89.2
	Medication	5	2.0
	Religious	3	1.2
Way to know about destinations	Newspaper	19	7.6
	TV	25	10.0
	Word of mouth	165	66.0
	Books	22	8.8
	Others	19	7.6

Sample Characteristics

Table 2 represents the frequency distribution of the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Demographic features include gender, age, occupation, education level, marital status, income level, number of visits, duration of stay, the reason for visiting, and ways to know about destinations. Among the respondents, the number of males was way more significant than females. The data shows that near about sixty-six percent of the respondents are less than 30 years old followed by the age group 30 to 40. Millennials (who are between 25-40) are easier to target, persuade even influence through social media. Fundamentally, the occupational status of the respondents is categorized into four groups namely student, business, service holder, and others. The number of respondents for these categories is 131, 13, 89, and 17 for the student, business, service holder and others respectively. It is observed that the highest number of respondents is single (63.6 percent). Now one of the main demographic characteristics of the respondents for this study is their number of visits. About 42% of them visited more than 5 times, then 33.3 and 24.4 of them visited 3-5 times and less than 3 times respectively. The highest number of respondents stayed less than 3 days in their visits. Only 12.8 percent of the respondents stayed more than 7 days at their destination. And in terms of their reason to visit, the respondents were given four options-business, tourism, medication and religious.89.2 percent said they visited for tourism purposes and the remaining percentage consisted of business, medication and religious purposes sequentially. Word of mouth was the way 66 percent of respondents knew about their destination. And very less significant ways were TV, newspaper and others.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factor analysis is used to identify the most relevant elements of a given construct, and it is a comprehensive process. Factor analysis evaluates the relationships between several variables. It defines high-interrelationship items (Hair et al, 2010). It helps reduce the number of items and choose the most relevant one. Several assumptions must be met before using factor analysis, which is also used to confirm data fitness. The result of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic suggests that there are no problems with the study's sample size distribution. It has been observed that the value of KMO is greater than .60, and the substantial value of Bartlett's test of sphericity indicates that it is appropriate for the investigation to move on to factor analysis.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.727
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1052.244
	df	190
	Sig.	.000

A reliability test was carried out in order to determine whether or not the several elements for a single construct were internally consistent with one another. In order to determine the level of internal consistency, the researchers relied on Cronbach's coefficient alpha as their criterion. In general, a Cronbach's alpha with a value of 0.60 is considered to be satisfactory (Churchill, 1979). It is clear from looking at table 3 that all of the constructs were able to surpass this threshold. In this investigation, a factor loading cut-off point of .40 was used, and this was done regardless of the size of the sample. This decision was made in accordance with the recommendations made by Pituch and Stevens (2015). Therefore, variables that had factor loadings that were less than .40 were omitted from Table 4. The process of forming a cluster or grouping of variables into discrete factors is what is meant by the term "factor extraction." The eigenvalue is a popular strategy that is utilized in the process of selecting the proper number of components. The predicted number of factors in research may be determined using either the latent root value or an eigenvalue that is higher than 1. (Malhotra, 2010). The aforementioned table has been presented to you, which has a total of eight criteria to consider. The components that were identified from the data are responsible for explaining about 70 percent of the overall variation. In the component matrix that has not been rotated, the vast majority of the variables are put into the first factor. In addition to that, a good number of the elements were cross loaded, which means they contributed to more than one build. Because of how the unrotated factor matrix is loaded, it is impossible to derive the consequential factors.

Linearity Test

In this study, linearity was tested using multiple regressions, and significance levels were analyzed to see which variables had the highest proportion of values that are larger than 0.05. The correlation matrix table was helpful in identifying the factors that were later eliminated from consideration. After that, the research looked to see whether there was any correlation between the variables that was more than 0.8. This was done so that the linearity problem could be observed. The analysis revealed that a correlational coefficient of .370 was the best possible value. Therefore, none of the items have the linearity issue.

Table 4: Factor Analysis Result of Items Measuring Tourist's satisfaction

Constructs and Related Items	Factor Loading	EigenValue (% of Variance Explained)	Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha)
Product			
<i>Diversity of tourist sites</i>	.802	3.959 (19.795)	.876
<i>Cleanness of tourist sites</i>	.735		
<i>Beauty of natural sites</i>	.711		
Price			
<i>Reflect the quality</i>	.826	1.905 (29.319)	.746
<i>Reasonable price</i>	.762		
<i>Willing to pay</i>	.750		
Place			
<i>Easy and convenient access</i>	.809	1.573 (37.186)	.798
<i>Availability of support service</i>	.752		
<i>Navigation between tourist sites</i>	.657		
Promotion			
<i>Aggressive promotion</i>	.779	1.513 (44.253)	.843
<i>Sufficient online information</i>	.693		
<i>Information helps to enrich knowledge</i>	.654		
People			
<i>Caring and cooperative tour operators</i>	.848	1.320 (50.850)	.703
<i>Skilled & interactive personnel</i>	.822		
Process			
<i>Consistency of service</i>	.830	1.199 (56.843)	.698
<i>Smooth delivery of value added service</i>	.790		
Physical Evidence			
<i>Well designed and decorated sites</i>	.813	1.153 (62.609)	.673
<i>Eco-friendly structured</i>	.694		
Tourists' Satisfaction			
<i>Exceeded expectations</i>	.827	1.010 (67.659)	.783
<i>Repeat visit to destinations</i>	.798		

Table 5: Person Correlations

	People	Price	Satisfaction	Process	Promotion	Product	Place	Physical Evidence
People	1							
Price	.145*	1						
Satisfaction	.094	.211**	1					
Process	.307**	.256**	.321**	1				
Promotion	.370**	.134*	.219**	.330**	1			
Product	.159*	.160*	.244**	.334**	.212**	1		
Place	.195**	.284**	.160*	.261**	.193**	.281**	1	.
Physical Evidence	.041	.136*	.245**	.170**	.133*	.118	.041	1

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to determine a line of "best fit" (Creswell, 2008) for several independent variables in the prediction or explanation of the dependent variable in the research. The study's research topic necessitated the use of this approach. All independent factors were shown to have substantial correlations with dependent variables in the previous study, but this analysis did not explain how these associations interacted to predict dependent

variables. In an effort to illustrate the influence of all service marketing mix elements on explaining tourist satisfaction, multiple regression analysis was performed. It is a statistical approach that investigates the combined influence of numerous factors to predict or explain an independent variable. The tourist satisfaction regression analysis is discussed in the next two parts. The computation was evaluated using SPSS Version 22. In particular, a stepwise linear multiple regression analysis was utilized. The regression model was estimated using the stepwise technique, which employs the best predictors. The results of the numerous regressions are discussed in the following sections.

Tourists' satisfaction regression model

According to the results of the multiple regression analysis, the elements of the service marketing mix (dependent variables) product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence combined together appear to explain tourists' satisfaction with $r = .623$, $r^2 = .579$, and adjusted $r^2 = .555$ respectively. The data were well-fit by the regression model, which received a F test score of 63.541 and was shown to be statistically significant at the $p .001$ level. The beta weights, also known as slopes, of each variable are included in Table 6, along with a constant representing the constituents of the marketing mix. The table provides not just unstandardized but also standardized coefficients, in addition to the t value and the degree of significance. The combination of the independent variables allows for the prediction of the level of satisfaction experienced by tourists that travel to eastern part of Bangladesh.

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.623 ^a	.579	.555	.57708

a. Predictors: (Constant), physical, place, people, product, price, promotion, process

Table 7: ANOVA Table

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17.580	7	2.511	63.541	.000 ^b
	Residual	80.592	242	.333		
	Total	98.172	249			

Dependent Variable: satisfaction

Predictors: (Constant), physical, place, people, product, price, promotion, process

Table 8: Multiple regression analysis predicting satisfaction in terms of service Marketing Mix Elements

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
	(Constant)	2.139	.280				7.649
People	.139	.048	.152	.810	.034	.815	1.227
Price	.268	.042	.303	1.645	.029	.873	1.146
Process	.359	.054	.400	2.960	.003	.745	1.342
Promotion	.289	.056	.305	1.604	.049	.794	1.259
Product	.193	.050	.219	1.873	.042	.837	1.195
Place	.222	.049	.329	.448	.041	.833	1.201
Physical Evidence	.356	.055	.470	2.847	.005	.950	1.053

According to the findings of the regression study, when the parts of the marketing mix are combined, all seven aspects can work together to predict the level of satisfaction that visitors would have toward the tourist destination of eastern part of Bangladesh. These factors are responsible for 63 percent of the variance in traveler satisfaction.

Hypothesis Discussion

The purpose of this study is to investigate the connection that exists between satisfactions and the components of the marketing mix. As we can see, the parts of the marketing mix have a substantial influence on the level of satisfaction experienced by tourists who have visited the eastern part of Bangladesh. This section is dedicated to the discussion of the outcomes.

Table 9: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis		Path Coefficients (β)	t-value	Results
Product	Tourist's Satisfaction	.219	1.873*	Supported
Price	Tourist's Satisfaction	.303	1.645*	Supported
Place	Tourist's Satisfaction	.329	.448*	Supported
Promotion	Tourist's Satisfaction	.305	1.604*	Supported
People	Tourist's Satisfaction	.152	.810*	Supported
Process	Tourist's Satisfaction	.400	2.960**	Supported
Physical Evidence	Tourist's Satisfaction	.470	2.847**	Supported

Hypothesis 1

The findings of the multiple regression analysis show that tourist satisfaction has a significant effect on product ($\beta = 0.219$, t value = 1.873, significant at the level of 0.05). These findings provide support for the first hypothesis and findings that are comparable to those reported in (Borden, 1984). According to these findings, when a product in the marketing mix parts is of sufficient quality, then tourists are more likely to be interested in purchasing it.

Hypothesis 2

There is a correlation between the cost of the services that visitors are paying for and their level of satisfaction with those services. Studies such as the ones conducted by (Peter and Donnelly, 2007) have demonstrated that tourists often make their purchasing decisions based on pricing. According to the findings of the regression analysis presented in Table 10, price had a significant influence on the tourist satisfaction ($\beta=0.0303$, t -value=1.645, significant at the threshold of 0.05). This research indicates, then, that the past findings that revealed the importance of the pricing of the items or services to satisfy tourists are further proven correct.

Hypothesis 3

Studies reveal a strong connection between a destination's appeal to tourists and its physical location. This study's multiple regression results suggest that ($\beta=0.329$, t -value=.448, significant at the level of 0.05), meaning that tourists' satisfaction with site has a substantial and positive association. It is clear from these results that distribution channels, locations, and modes of transportation as well as inventories are all interconnected (Ariwa and Syvertsen, 2010).

Hypothesis 4

The promotion of a product or service has a considerable impact on the degree to which a consumer is satisfied (Munusamy and Hoo, 2008). According to the findings of multiple regressions, the country of origin had a substantial and positive connection between

promotion and satisfaction ($\beta = 0.305$, t -value = 1.604, significant at the threshold of 0.05), showing that the association was significant. This is true in accordance with the research carried out by (Al-hroot, 2007). These findings lend credence to hypothesis number 4.

Hypothesis 5

Overall tourist satisfaction has a favorable association with individuals, according to the findings of this study. $\beta=0.152$, $t=1.810$, t -value significant at 0.05 level of significance. Tourist orientation cannot be achieved without active cooperation (Judd, 2001). The quality of a service is largely dependent on the quality of the people who provide it.

Hypothesis 6

Regression results from this study show that the overall satisfaction of tourists is positively correlated with the procedure. This is a clear indicator of how quickly and effectively the service providers are doing their job, and this is what makes the consumer happy with their purchase. Hirankitti and colleagues (2009). The relationship is significant ($\beta = 0.400$; t -value 2.960, significant at the level of 0.01 authenticating the findings the study by Saydan (2013). Since prior studies demonstrated that procedure is a key factor in tourists' satisfaction, this study confirms the findings.

Hypothesis 7

It is consistent with prior research that H8 (physical evidence) is accepted (Rafiq and Ahmed, 1995). That tangible evidence has a positive correlation with overall satisfaction ($\beta=0.470$; t -value=2.847, significant at the level 0.01), according to this study. All prior research show that tourists are happy if physical evidence is well-placed. It is also critical for the tourist firm to ensure that the physical evidence used to evaluate the products or services is properly positioned.

Discussion of the Findings

This study shed some relevant light on the process of finding the components of the service marketing mix that have an effect on the level of satisfaction experienced by visitors in the eastern area. As a result of the fact that the purpose of this part is to create an analysis of the fundamental results of the study in the line of a wider body of relevant information, the comparative analysis of the outcome is made in comparison with the theories or pre-existing understanding of the facts. The primary purpose of this current research is to explore the influence of different parts of service marketing mix on the level of satisfaction experienced by visitors to tourism attractions in area. According to the results of the study, the product, the price, the venue, the advertising, the people, the process, and the physical proof are the primary motivators that impact consumer satisfaction in tourism destinations, particularly from the standpoint of eastern area. The level of satisfaction experienced by a company's target audience is significantly impacted by each component of the service marketing mix. The results of this study show that the alternative hypothesis is more likely to be true than the null hypothesis, which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. The process and physical evidence from the elements of the service marketing mix are the most influential variable, significant at the level of 0.05, while the rest of the elements are important at the level of 0.01.

Limitations and Future Research

It's important to keep in mind that this analysis has a few flaws. First and foremost, because the focus of this study is on visitor satisfaction, it is possible that survey respondents would submit inaccurate or misleading information, which will have an impact on the study's findings and interpretation. Second, respondents seldom reveal their genuine selves in surveys, which

is a major drawback of this type of study. In addition, the sample size may have been increased because eastern receives an enormous number of tourists every day, and the findings cannot be extrapolated to the entire population of tourists in the city. Fourth The study's time was also a drawback. During the busiest times of the year, data was collected. Only seven factors were included in the study; other factors, such as production and quality, politics, and scarcity, may have been included as well. However, the service marketing mix aspects may have a wider influence on other possible areas of company, such as tourists' satisfaction, which is the topic of this study article. In addition, this study was done exclusively in eastern, which means that a comparable poll may provide intriguing results in other tourist sites. Factor analysis and multiple regression analysis were used in the study's conclusion. Other sophisticated statistical approaches and tools can be utilized to discover the link between variables.

Recommendations:

Bangladesh is a country of huge possibilities in the tourism sector because of its serene natural beauty. Covid-19 may have seemingly put a stall on its growth but it can be recovered by ensuring the continuous tourist-centrist improvement in the elements of 7P by the marketers. The official website of Bangladesh Tourism Board does not even recognize some of the most visited tourist spots of eastern part like Cumilla. This pandemic has made us dependent on online in almost every aspect of our lives, so while deciding, people search their destinations online. hence the writers recommend the government and respective ministry to maintain their online presence. The natural beauty of the places has to be ensured in terms of safety-security and maintaining the cleanliness of the places. Lastly, the tourist marketers must work on their strategies to promote the tourist-oriented service designs, so that there is no miscommunication or gap in the process.

Conclusion:

This study aims to identify the relationship service marketing mix has with the satisfaction level of the tourists visiting eastern part of Bangladesh during Covid-19. To be more precise the objective was to find out the aspects of the eastern part of Bangladesh those contribute to the overall positive experience that visitors have there, how much the 7P of service marketing mix influence their satisfaction level and lastly the ways tourism marketers can influence the degree of satisfaction of the tourists by redefining the elements of the service marketing mix. Gathered data from the tourists who visited the eastern part of Bangladesh was measured by building a seven-factor model and using multivariate regression. From the study it can be said that the elements of service marketing mix made a significant impact on the satisfaction level of the tourists who visited the eastern part of Bangladesh. It was hypothesized in the study that product and tourist satisfaction have a positive relationship and this was well accepted on the ground that people are more likely to visit the spots that maintains its serenity naturally and cleanly. In addition to that, the study shows the significant influence price, place, promotion, physical evidence, process, people have on tourists' satisfaction. It can be concluded from the findings that among the 7P of marketing mix, Physical Evidence and Process is the most influential in determining the degree of satisfaction level of the tourists during the epidemic.

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